

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

Airth

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The postal survey aimed to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

63 participants from Airth, Skinflats and Grangemouth (9.5% response rate)

16% aged 18-44

60% aged 45-74

24% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast
(Inner Forth) = **1.48 km**

Mean distance to other rivers =
0.77 km

experienced
flooding and/or
erosion

have noticed
coastal change

concerned about
climate change

have not heard
about nature-
based solutions

would accept
managed realignment
if people are not
displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Planning restrictions

“Limit development as we are already on a flood plain”

2 A mix of options

“A mix of options is likely to be required to achieve effective local protection without adverse impacts on adjacent coastline”

3 Restoration/recreation of natural habitats

“Natural defenses tend to be more sustainable in the longer term and can have a climate positive impact”

not confident they can influence local decisions

do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among Airth respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>

Project funders:

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